

Increasing Job Satisfaction Through Strengthening Situational Leadership, Organizational Culture, And The Need For Achievement: Empirical Study On Private Junior High School Teachers In South Jakarta

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Situational Leadership, Organizational Culture, Need For Achievement, And Job Satisfaction</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5576641</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this research is to produce ways and strategies to increase teacher job satisfaction through the identification of the strengths of the relationship between situational leadership, organizational culture, and achievement needs with job satisfaction of private junior high school teachers in South Jakarta. This research uses a combination research method between Correlational Research and SITOREM Analysis. The quantitative research phase was carried out using a survey method with a correlational approach and data collection was carried out through a questionnaire. then explained by statistical analysis and analyzed by regression and correlation analysis. The population of this research is the Permanent Teachers of the A-Accredited Private Junior High School Foundation in South Jakarta, totaling 418 people. The research sample of 205 respondents was determined using the Taro Yamane formula, selected using the proportional random sampling method. The results of quantitative research found that situational leadership that emphasizes the leader's instruction style, leader consultation style, leader participation style, leader delegation style can increase teacher job satisfaction. An organizational culture that promotes innovation and risk taking, attention to detail, results orientation, people orientation, team orientation, aggressiveness, and stability can increase teacher job satisfaction. The need for achievement that emphasizes the aspects of responsibility, feedback, co-workers who are in tune, completion of assignments, rational goals, and quality of appearance can increase teacher job satisfaction.</i></p>

Introduction

Education is a human effort to broaden the horizon of knowledge in order to form values, attitudes and behavior. As an effort that not only yields great benefits, education is also one of the basic human needs that are often felt to have not reached an expectation. For example, formal education is expected to produce graduates who meet the criteria for the demands of available jobs, moreover these graduates can create new jobs as a practice of mastering the knowledge they have gained from educational institutions. This condition is still not fulfilled and is one of the descriptions of the low quality of our education. One of the most important influences in the world of Indonesian education is the existence of teachers as educators and teachers who will direct the nation's generation in the right and right direction. Teachers are the most important part in the teaching and learning process. The quality or quality of education is largely determined by the quality of learning in schools. In school learning, in this case in the classroom, the teacher plays a very important role. For that we need teachers who are really able to master the learning process so that the quality of education in the education unit is in accordance with the expectations of the community. The reality at this time is not an easy matter of presenting teachers with the roles and functions that are expected in the future. The appearance of teachers in the future is expected to occupy a better position, so that they are able to carry out their duties. With the bigger challenges, problems, duties and responsibilities, the expectation of better conditions for teachers is not an exaggeration.

Teacher job satisfaction will be shown through the teacher's behavior by showing an attitude of pleasure or displeasure with the work he does. If the teacher is satisfied with what is obtained from the school where he works, then the teacher will provide results that exceed the target as well as if the teacher is not satisfied with what is obtained from the school, the teacher's work results will not be as expected. The teacher's self can be said to be a sufficient factor to determine the teacher's performance is not optimal. In addition, the compensation or facilities provided by the government are inadequate. For example, appreciation for teacher achievement, facilities for carrying out work, support for developing according to interests and talents, incentives or compensation to support teacher welfare, teacher involvement in school development, support for improving educational qualifications and competencies, and harmony in the work

environment. Given the importance of the teacher's role in improving the quality of education, it is highly expected that there will be attention, listening and motivation by various parties so that they can carry out their duties with enthusiasm, responsibility, and sincerity to educate the next generation of quality and noble character.

METHODS

The research method used is a survey method with a correlational approach, namely to determine the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The research variable consisted of three independent variables, namely situational leadership (X1), organizational culture (X2) and achievement needs (X3) with the dependent variable being teacher job satisfaction (Y). To obtain data in the field used measuring instruments (instruments) in the form of a questionnaire that was compiled based on the indicators contained in the research variables. The primary data needed is data on situational leadership, organizational culture, achievement needs and teacher job satisfaction. The population of this research is the Permanent Teachers of the A-credited Private Junior High School Foundation in South Jakarta based on data from the South Jakarta City Education Sub-Department in 2020 totaling 418 teachers spread over 10 sub-districts and 96 schools. Sampling technique or sampling is a way to determine the size of the research sample so that the sample taken can truly represent the entire population. In this study, samples were taken from an affordable population by using a proportional random sampling technique.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The research data presented in this section were obtained from the results of measurements of job satisfaction, situational leadership, organizational culture and achievement needs based on the responses of respondents to the items of the variable instrument. The data was collected from a sample of 205 private junior high school (SMP) teachers in South Jakarta spread over 10 sub-districts and 96 schools.

Hypothesis test

Testing the hypothesis of this study using regression and correlation formulas. The first, second and third hypotheses were analyzed by simple regression and correlation formulas. After that, the next step is to analyze the correlation using Multiple Regression. The details of the results of testing each hypothesis are as follows.

Relationship between Situational Leadership (X1) and Job Satisfaction (Y)

Based on the results of a simple linear regression analysis between the pair of situational leadership data (variable X1) and job satisfaction (variable Y), it is known that the regression coefficient b obtained is 0.59 and the constant a value is 57.68.

Table 1. Results of Significant Correlation Tests Between Situational Leadership Variables with Job Satisfaction Variables and Significance Test t

n	r_{y1}	t_{hitung}	$t_{tabel}^{(2)}$		Conclusion
			0,05	0,01	
205	0,701	13,998**	1,658	2,617	Very Significant

The results of the simple relationship analysis mean that there is a positive relationship between situational leadership and job satisfaction. Thus, it can be concluded that the better the situational leadership carried out by the principal on a teacher, the higher the teacher's job satisfaction. The findings in this study at the same time reject H_0 which states "there is no positive relationship between situational leadership and job satisfaction and accept H_1 which states there is a positive relationship between situational leadership and job satisfaction". The strength of the relationship between situational leadership (variable X1) and job satisfaction (variable Y) can be seen from the calculation of the coefficient of determination. The magnitude of the coefficient of determination is 0.49. This magnitude gives the understanding that 49% of the variation in job satisfaction can be explained by variations in situational leadership

Relationship between Organizational Culture (X2) and Job Satisfaction (Y)

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis between pairs of organizational culture data (variable X2) and job satisfaction (variable Y), it is known that the regression coefficient b obtained is 0.73 and the constant a value is 31.45.

Table 2. Significant Test Results of Correlation Between Organizational Culture Variables and Job Satisfaction Variables and Significance Test t

n	r_{y2}	t_{hitung}	$t_{tabel}^{(2)}$		Conclusion
			0,05	0,01	
205	0,721	14,824**	1,658	2,617	Very Sig

The results of the simple relationship analysis mean that there is a positive relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction. Thus it can be concluded that the better the organizational culture of a teacher, the higher the job satisfaction of the teacher. The findings in this study at the same time reject H_0 which states "there is no positive relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction and accept H_1 which states there is a positive relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction". The strength of the relationship between organizational culture (variable X2) and job satisfaction (variable Y) can be seen from the calculation of the coefficient of determination. The magnitude of the coefficient of determination is 0.52. This magnitude provides an understanding that 52% of variations in job satisfaction can be explained by variations in organizational culture.

Relationship between Achievement Needs (X3) and Job Satisfaction (Y)

Based on the results of simple linear regression analysis between the pair of achievement needs data (variable X3) and job satisfaction (variable Y), it is known that the regression coefficient b obtained is 0.64 and the constant a value is 41.12.

Table 3. Summary of Significant Test Results Correlation Between Achievement Needs Variables with Job Satisfaction Variables and t Significance Test

n	r_{y3}	t_{hitung}	$t_{tabel}^{(2)}$		Conclusion
			0,05	0,01	
205	0,700	13,980**	1,658	2,617	Very sig

The results of the simple relationship analysis mean that there is a positive relationship between the need for achievement and job satisfaction. Thus, it can be concluded that the higher the need for achievement of a teacher, the higher the job satisfaction of the teacher. The findings in this study at the same time reject H_0 which states "there is no positive relationship between achievement needs and job satisfaction and accept H_1 which states there is a positive relationship between achievement needs and job satisfaction". The strength of the relationship between the need for achievement (variable X3) and job satisfaction (variable Y) can be seen from the calculation of the coefficient of determination. The magnitude of the coefficient of determination is 0.49. This magnitude provides an understanding that 49% of the variation in job satisfaction can be explained by variations in achievement needs.

Partial Correlation Test

The calculation of the partial correlation test of the relationship between situational leadership (X1) and job satisfaction (Y) with the control of the organizational culture variable (X2), the obtained partial correlation coefficient $r_{y1.2} = 0.274$ (weak relationship strength) and significance test $t_{count} = 4.059$ while $t_{table} (dk = 202; = 0.05) = 1.658$, because $t_{count} > t_{table} (4.059 > 1.658)$ it is significant. In the simple correlation coefficient found $r_{y1} = 0.701$ (strong relationship strength). In this case, there was a significant decrease in the strength of the relationship (from a strong relationship of 0.701 to a weak relationship of 0.274). It means that the relationship between situational leadership and job satisfaction is significantly influenced by organizational culture.

Thus the calculation of the partial correlation of situational leadership, organizational culture and achievement needs with job satisfaction can be described in the following table 4:

Table 4. Calculation Results of Partial Correlation Test

Control	Partial	Sig test		Conclusion	
		t_{hitung}	$t_{tabel}^{(2)}$		
			$\alpha=0,05$		$\alpha=0,01$
(X ₁) and (Y)					

X ₂	0,274	4,059	1,658	2,617	Very Sig
X ₃	0,378	5,817	1,658	2,617	Very Sig
(X ₂) and (Y)					
X ₁	0,356	5,428	1,658	2,617	Very Sig
X ₃	0,401	6,237	1,658	2,617	Very Sig
(X ₃) and (Y)					
X ₁	0,377	5,799	1,658	2,617	Very Sig
X ₂	0,331	4,998	1,658	2,617	Very Sig

Discussion

The contribution of situational leadership factors to job satisfaction in this study can be seen from the coefficient of determination $r^2_{y1} = 0.491$, which means that situational leadership contributes 49% to job satisfaction, while the remaining 51% is determined by other variables. Based on these data it can be said that the increase in situational leadership will affect the increase in job satisfaction. The results of this study are supported by the theory stated by Daft (2008:71-72) which says that in situational leadership, there are 4 (four) components of a leader's behavior, namely; 1) the behavior of providing specific and clear task directions, 2) the behavior of the leader who explains the duties of his followers and asks his followers to clarify the given task, 3) the behavior of the leader who invites his followers to jointly discuss the work and make decisions, and 4) gives authority and responsibility to followers to complete tasks.

The results of this study are in line with the theory proposed by Ivancevich et.al. (2012:12) who said that "however, unsatisfied employee do tend to quit more often, to be absent more frequently, and to produce lower quality work than satisfied workers." (Employees who are dissatisfied tend to be more resigned and absent, and produce work that is not of high quality than employees who have high job satisfaction). Meanwhile, Robbins and Judge (2013:520) say that: "We find a consistent negative relationship between satisfaction and absenteeism, but it is moderate to weak." (Agree with the negative correlation between job satisfaction with absenteeism and resignation). This means that someone with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards his work. Satisfied teachers are more likely to speak positively about the organization, help others, and far exceed the normal expectations of their work. Based on the results of this study, the contribution of the need for achievement to job satisfaction can be seen from the value of the coefficient of determination $r^2_{y3} = 0.491$, which means that the need for achievement contributes 49% to teacher job satisfaction, while the remaining 51% is determined by other variables. The magnitude of this correlation coefficient indicates the strength of the relationship between the need for achievement and job satisfaction is relatively high, and referring to the results of research data analysis, it can be said that an increase in the strength of the need for achievement will be associated with an increase in job satisfaction. The results of this study are also in accordance with research conducted by UnikaPrihatsanti (2010: pp. 78-86) entitled "The Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Need for Achievement with Resistance to Change Tendencies in Undip Semarang Lecturers" concludes that there is a very significant positive relationship ($r = 0.197$ $p < 0.01$) between need for achievement and lecturer job satisfaction.

Based on the analysis of this research data, it is known that the contribution of situational leadership and organizational culture factors together to job satisfaction can be seen from the value of the coefficient of determination $r^2_{y1.2} = 0.556$, so it can be said that situational leadership and organizational culture together contribute 56% on job satisfaction, so the remaining 44% is determined by the operation of other variables. This means that it can be concluded that, the increase in the strength of situational leadership and organizational culture together will be associated with an increase in job satisfaction. The findings obtained in this study indicate that if the teacher has a good perception of situational leadership carried out by the principal supported by the need for good achievement, the teacher will have a positive attitude regarding various aspects of feelings related to work. Thus, a teacher who has situational leadership and the need for good achievement together will be able to increase job satisfaction. Based on the results of this study, the contribution of situational leadership factors, organizational culture and achievement needs together to job satisfaction can be seen from the coefficient of determination $r^2_{y1.2.3} = 0.588$ which means that situational leadership, organizational culture and achievement needs together contribute 59% to job satisfaction, while the remaining 41% is determined by other variables. The findings obtained in this study indicate that if the teacher at work has a good perception of situational leadership applied by the principal who is supported by a good organizational culture and coupled with the need for good achievement, then job satisfaction will also increase. Thus a teacher who has a good perception of situational leadership applied by the principal and a good organizational culture with the support of good achievement needs will also increase job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

After conducting the quantitative research stage through the process of analyzing the results of data processing, statistical calculations, hypothesis testing and discussion of research results which were then strengthened by SITOREM analysis, the research has succeeded in finding ways and strategies for Increasing Job Satisfaction Through Strengthening Situational Leadership Culture, Organizational Culture and Achievement Needs . The results of correlational statistical analysis are as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between situational leadership and teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of situational leadership, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening situational leadership can increase job satisfaction.
2. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between organizational culture and teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of organizational culture, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening organizational culture can increase job satisfaction.
3. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between achievement needs and teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of need for achievement, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening the need for achievement can increase job satisfaction.
4. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between situational leadership and organizational culture together with teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of situational leadership and the higher the level of organizational culture, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening situational leadership and organizational culture can increase job satisfaction.
5. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between situational leadership and achievement needs together with teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of situational leadership and the higher the level of need for achievement, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening situational leadership and need for achievement can increase job satisfaction.
6. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between organizational culture and achievement needs together with teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of organizational culture and the higher the level of need for achievement, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening organizational culture and achievement needs can increase job satisfaction.
7. There is a positive and significant relationship with a moderate level of relationship strength between situational leadership, organizational culture and achievement needs together with teacher job satisfaction. This means that the higher the level of situational leadership, the higher the level of organizational culture, and the higher the level of need for achievement, the higher the job satisfaction of teachers. Thus strengthening situational leadership, organizational culture and need for achievement can increase job satisfaction.

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